

PAREMIOLOGY - AS THE BASIS OF NATIONAL CULTURE OF THE PEOPLE

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Abstract: This article analyses the paremiology, paremiological units and their role in contrastive linguistics. In linguistics, the field of paremiology is one of the fields with a long history. It was studied as part of lexicology for many years until it was separated as a separate department. Despite the fact that a lot of research has been done in the field of paremiology, it still has many aspects that have not yet been discovered.

Key words: proverbs, sayings, paremiological units, paremia, ethnolinguistics.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются паремиология, паремиологические единицы и их роль в контрастивном языкознании. В лингвистике область паремиологии является одной из областей с давней историей. Его изучали в рамках лексикологии долгие годы, пока не выделили в отдельную кафедру. Несмотря на то, что в области паремиологии проведено немало исследований, в ней еще есть много аспектов, которые еще не открыты.

Ключевые слова: пословицы, поговорки, паремиологические единицы, паремия, этнолингвистика.

Paremiology is the study of proverbs and sayings. It is a branch of linguistics that focuses on the origin, meaning, and usage of proverbs in different cultures and languages. Paremiology seeks to understand the social and cultural contexts in which proverbs are used, as well as their impact on communication and language development.

Proverbs are short, pithy sayings that convey a message or moral lesson. They are often based on common experiences and observations, and are used to express wisdom, advice, or criticism. Proverbs can be found in almost every language and culture, and are an important part of oral tradition.

Paremiologists study proverbs in a variety of contexts, including literature, folklore, and everyday speech. They analyze the structure and content of proverbs, as well as their usage in different situations. Paremiology also explores the role of proverbs in shaping cultural identity and values.

Paremiology is the study of proverbs and other forms of folk literature. It is the academic discipline that focuses on the origin, history, and usage of proverbs. Here are some examples of how to use paremiology in a sentence:

- According to the principles of paremiology, proverbs are an essential part of every language and culture.
- The research conducted in the field of paremiology has shed light on the cultural significance of proverbs.
- Paremiology has helped linguists understand the evolution of language through the study of proverbs.

As you can see from these examples, paremiology is used to refer to the study of proverbs and other forms of folk literature. It is often used in academic and scholarly contexts.

The study of proverbs is called paremiology (from Greek παροιμία - paroimía, "proverb") and can be dated back as far as Aristotle. Paremiography, on the other hand, is the collection of proverbs. A prominent proverb scholar in the United States is Wolfgang Mieder. He has written or edited over 50 books on the subject, edits the journal *Proverbium*, has written innumerable articles on proverbs, and is very widely cited by other proverb scholars.

A similar form is proverbial expressions ("to bite the dust"). The difference is that proverbs are unchangeable sentences, while proverbial expressions permit alterations to fit the grammar of the context. Another close construction is an allusion to a proverb, such as

(ST) "The new broom will sweep clean"

(TT) «Новая метла метет по новому»

(ST) "Hunger is the best cook"

(TT) «Голод – лучший повар»

To make the respective statement more general most proverbs are based on a metaphor. Further typical features of the proverb are its shortness (average: seven words), and the fact that its author is generally unknown (otherwise it would be a quotation).

Proverbs are used by speakers for a variety of purposes. Sometimes they are used as a way of saying something gently, in a veiled way. Other times, they are used to carry more weight in a discussion; a weak person is able to enlist the tradition of the ancestors to support his position. Proverbs can also be used to simply make a conversation/discussion livelier. In many parts of the world, the use of proverbs is a mark of being a good orator.

The study of proverbs has application in a number of fields. Clearly, those who study folklore and literature are interested in them, but scholars from a variety of fields have found ways to profitably incorporate the study proverbs. For example, they have been used to study abstract reasoning of children, acculturation of immigrants, intelligence, the differing mental processes in mental illness, cultural themes, etc. Proverbs have also been incorporated into the strategies of social workers, teachers, preachers, and even politicians.

Proverbial expressions have been given a variety of labels: adages, dictums, maxims, mottoes, precepts, saws, truisms. The terms all convey the notion of a piece of traditional wisdom, handed down by previous generations. In most cases, the origin of a proverb is unknown.

The effectiveness of a proverb lies largely in its brevity and directness. The syntax is simple, the images vivid, and the allusions domestic, and thus easy to understand. Memorability is aided through the use of alliteration, rhythm, and rhyme

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